

Conference Report for SPNHC-TDWG 2024

By Siobhan Leachman ([User:Ambrosia10](#))

ORCID: [0000-0002-5398-7721](#)

Introduction

Siobhan Leachman ([User:Ambrosia10](#)) obtained funding from Wikimedia Aotearoa New Zealand (WANZ) to attend and present at the joint [Society for the Preservation of Natural History Collections](#) (SPNHC) and the [Biodiversity Information Standards](#) (TDWG) 2024 conference in Okinawa, Japan.

The conference was held from the 2nd to the 6th September 2024 at the Okinawa Convention Center. The conference website can be found here <https://www.tdwg.org/conferences/2024/>.

This report will cover those presentations I attended in person. Videos of all the sessions have been added to Youtube and will be publically available in 6 months time. As a registered conference attendee I will be able to view the recordings of the parallel sessions I was not able to attend prior to that public release date but these recorded presentations will not be covered in this report.

Extended abstract

Lucy Schrader ([User:Avocadobabygirl](#)) and I prepared an abstract on our [Wikidata WikiProject Te Papa research expeditions project](#) which was accepted by the conference organisers.

Subsequent to this we were invited to give this presentation immediately after the first keynote to all the attendees of the conference from both the SPNHC and TDWG communities. To take advantage of this opportunity we were required to create an extended abstract for our presentation. This extended abstract was accepted and was published prior to the conference in the Biodiversity Information Science and Standards journal. The article can be found at this link.

<https://doi.org/10.3897/biss.8.135809>

I shared this publication widely on my social media accounts including X (twitter), Bluesky, and LinkedIn accounts. I also created a Wikidata item for this publication <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q130212138> and have also uploaded the publication into Wikimedia Commons

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Delving_Into_Te_Papa_Research_Expedition_Data.pdf.

Te Papa Research Expeditions Presentation

I presented our co-authored presentation on the 2nd of September. The slides and script of this presentation can be found in Zenodo

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13631553> and the slides and script have also been uploaded into Wikimedia Commons, see

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Slides_-_Delving_Into_Te_Papa_Research_Expedition_Data.pdf and

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Script_-_Delving_into_Te_Papa_Research_Expedition_Data.pdf. A recording of this presentation will be available for general release on Youtube in 6 months.

Our presentation was the first presentation after the two initial keynotes from Dr Sara Beerly and Tom Strang. It was very well received with multiple attendees discussing the presentation and its subject with me during the conference. There were also engagement opportunities that resulted from Sabine von Mering's presentation, co-authored by Sabine, myself and several of our colleagues, on the overarching research expeditions Wikiproject and the associated TDWG modelling expeditions task group.

TDWG Modelling Expedition Task group presentation

Sabine von Mering presented on WikiProject Research Expeditions

https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:WikiProject_Research_expeditions and the TDWG Modelling Expeditions Task group

<https://www.tdwg.org/community/cd/expeditions/>. This presentation was

co-authored by Sabine, myself and a variety of other participants in the project. The presentation slides can be found here

https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1x-qH2RvxuysaAVr4bPoYcnArj2UPPRHhCgB_EHE1Cwl/edit?usp=sharing and a recording of the presentation will again be

available for general release on Youtube in 6 months.

Overall impression of the conference

This was the first joint conference for the SPNHC and TDWG communities since 2018, an event at which I also had the opportunity to attend. Since that time there has been significant uptake, particularly amongst the TDWG community, of Wikidata. The use of Wikidata QIDs as an identifier for people has been prevalent, but during this conference I was involved in or witnessed discussions detailing the use of Wikidata in globally linking or reconciling taxonomic names.

I also noticed, in comparison to last year, that there was more awareness of Wikidata amongst the SPNHC community. The SPNHC portion of the conference tends to be made up more of curators and collection managers rather than those with a basis of biodiversity informatics knowledge. I noticed I no longer had to explain what Wikidata was to established career attendees. Everyone I talked to was well aware of the usefulness of Wikidata. This Wikidata knowledge seems to me to result from institutions and individuals making use of the Bionomia website <https://bionomia.net/> to link their specimens to the identifiers of collectors. This includes the Wikidata Qid for deceased collectors. However I had several conversations with early career professionals where I found I had to explain what Wikidata was and how useful it is for institutions as well as the use of QIDs in collection management systems.

Personal Conference highlights

The major conference highlight for me was the ability to catch up with colleagues and collaborators in person. I had multiple conversations with established contacts in the TDWG and SPNHC communities, obtaining updates on their work and projects being undertaken. These included conversations with conference participants such as Shelley James, Alison Vaughan, Deb Paul, Rod Page, Nicole Kearney, (the last two who work with the Biodiversity Heritage Library Permanent Identifiers working group) Holly Little and Libby Ellwood to name but a few.

The conference also provided an opportunity to meet new contacts. I was particularly pleased to meet Ricky-Lee Erickson the Collection Manager, Land Vertebrates and Gallery Renewal from Auckland War Memorial Museum. I also met and discussed Wikidata and how it might enrich their particular use cases/workflows with [James Mickley](#) (Assistant Professor of Practice (Herbarium Curator) at Oregon State University) and with [Anton Güntsch](#) (Director, Center for Biodiversity Informatics and Collection Data Integration (Botanic Garden and Botanical Museum Berlin). I also discussed the possibility of a Wikidata and Bionomia workshop with [Yi-Ming Gan](#) during an upcoming GBIF node meeting .

Day 1 Sessions

As for sessions and presentations, I enjoyed the first conference keynote by [Dr Sara Beerly](#), Massachusetts Institute of Technology, titled *Challenges and Opportunities at the Intersection of AI and Biodiversity*. Her presentation on AI and biodiversity data was fascinating. Many of the challenges she discussed have arisen during other projects I have been involved in and the AI solutions she proposed were extremely interesting.

One challenge she discussed that both AI and humans are currently grappling with is the lack of an up-to-date agreed global database of taxonomic names. This is a pervasive challenge for both AI and humans. It has certainly arisen within the Biodiversity Heritage Library (BHL)-Wiki working group (BHL-Wiki working group) https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:WikiProject_BHL particularly when participants are adding depicts statements to the Structured Data on Commons (SDC) on BHL sourced illustrations. The lack of an agreed global taxonomic database as well as the existence of taxonomic synonyms have exacerbated how we model taxon items in Wikidata and then use those items in Wikimedia Commons when adding structured data to images.

Rod Page's presentation at the conference *Lazy knowledge graphs and the "extended phenotype" of taxonomy* discussed citations and the work of taxonomists. I particularly enjoyed his "rant" about the lack of digital links between taxon names and the literature that created them. Page pointed out that only 2% of taxa in GBIF have a digital link to their original description or scholarly article containing the same. I am aware that the Wiki biodiversity community is attempting to assist with this linking. Contributions to Wikidata can help solve this issue by digitally linking the taxon name item to the scholarly article that established that name and goes a long way to assisting the creation of an agreed global taxonomic database.

For an example of a Wikidata item that shows the digital linking of the taxonomic name to the scholarly article that established that name see <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q5045910>

Day 2 Sessions

I spent much of Day 2 in the multiple AI related sessions learning more about how Artificial Intelligence and large language models are being used in the Biodiversity data community. The following presentations were of particular interest to me.

Integrating LLMs and the iDigBio portal for conversational data exploration and inference by Michael Elliott, Manuel Luciano, José Fortes

The species occurrence and image aggregator iDigBio <https://www.idigbio.org/> has recognised that their search function on their platform is easy to use but inflexible. It also recognised that their API is very flexible but hard for non coders to use. iDigBio is therefore trailing using their own chatbot to assist with searching their records. See <https://chat.idigbio.org>. This has the potential for being useful in species Wiki work empowering editors to extract data from the iDigBio portal. I had an opportunity to test chatbot and it appears to work well but like most chatbots the data it supplies needs to be double checked. We were also warned the tool can break. Still, I was impressed.

Transcribing Specimen Labels using AI Large Language Models: Vouching for Vouchervision by James Mickley, Alexandria Kurowski and William Weaver. CC BY 4.0

This initiative was of interest as I began my citizen science work transcribing specimen labels and it was fascinating to see this project using AI and Large Language Models to undertake this transcription work converting the label into OCR text and then splitting the text into its component parts and fitting them into fields that comply with the Darwin Core standard for biodiversity data.

James Mickley explained that after this process they undertook data checking and then cleaning work with OpenRefine improving the data to 90% complete. This workflow significantly decreased the cost of transcribing and then transforming the OCR into appropriately formatted data relating to each specimen. However quality control checking was still definitely needed. He also analysed 6 different Large Language Models using this workflow and confirmed there was not a lot of difference between models.

The element of this talk that surprised me was that Mickley appeared to only use OpenRefine for data cleaning and quality control. He didn't mention using OpenRefine for reconciling, and certainly not reconciling against Wikidata, to obtain identifiers for the Darwin Core terms "recorded by id" or "identified by id". This meant that collectors and determiners of specimens continued to exist in his collection management system as name strings only.

When I discussed this with James Mickley later that day I was extremely surprised to learn that his collection management system does not currently have a place to add people identifiers. However he understands that this is coming in the very near future.

I had a couple more conversations with him during the conference. As a result of these I supplied him with "how to" documentation sourced from the Hidden Figures CURE work <https://qubeshub.org/publications/4523/1> I have been undertaking with Makenzie Mabry. He was particularly interested in obtaining "how to" documentation to teach senior collectors who visited his herbarium to obtain an ORCID. I also sent him "how to" documentation generated by both the [Hidden Figures CURE project](#) as well as "how to" documentation generated by [Wikidata WikiProject IBC 2024](#) so he can teach students about Wikidata and then reuse any collector Wikidata items generated in Bionomia. I am hopeful this will encourage him to replace his collector name strings with appropriate identifiers - that is either the Wikidata QID for deceased collectors or ORCID for living collectors.

Lessons learned from SISRIS, a US-based initiative to support inclusive and sustainable collections-based research infrastructure for systematics by [Andrea Weeks](#) , Elizabeth Collins , Twanelle W. Majors, Zack E. Murrell, Deborah Paul, Matthew Sheik, David P. Shorthouse, Shawn Zeringue-Krosnick.

SISRIS was an initiative to undertake outreach with the botany community teaching them how to contribute to [Bionomia](#). This was of particular interest to me as this initiative based their [“how to” documentation](#) on a [now out of date document](#) I had produced for the Auckland War Memorial Museum. Bionomia uses Wikidata QIDs as the appropriate identifier when the collector is deceased. It was interesting to learn more about the impact of this outreach and upskilling effort as I believe it had a flow on effect. Anecdotally it appeared to interest botanists in Wikidata and in my opinion helped ensure they were aware of Wikidata prior to I and my colleagues outreach and upskilling in Wikidata efforts with our Wikidata WikiProject IBC 2024 https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:WikiProject_IBC_2024. This presentation was a timely reminder for me to carve out time to update the Auckland War Memorial Museum Bionomia instructions <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3908726> and upload that new version to Zenodo.

Day 3 Sessions

Of particular interest to me were the multiple presentations in the session entitled **Catalogue of Life as a Means to Harmonise and Unify Taxonomic Data Services**. The reason for this is that I am a contributor to the Catalogue of Life (CoL) as a result of a workflow I use for both my Wikipedia and Wikidata editing. The CoL identifier is also an important identifier to add to taxa items in Wikidata.

The CoL is an initiative to create a complete authoritative list of the world’s species. It has the potential to be the solution to the issue I have discussed previously and which was one of the main challenges addressed during the conference, that is, the lack of up-to-date agreed global database of taxonomic names. The CoL provides the taxonomic backbone for the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) <https://www.gbif.org/>.

This set of presentations taught me much about the [CoL data pipeline](#) as well as more about [ChecklistBank](#), the repository of taxonomic datasets used to help create the CoL. I have gone into some detail about several of these presentations not just to facilitate a reporting back to the Wiki community but also to ensure I have detailed notes concerning these presentations for future use.

The presenter noted that genera can often lack genus authorship in datasets and that when merging datasets it helps if this authorship is added. This is because it is one of the elements used to detect the appropriate nomenclature code. For example if the genus taxon is formatted as a zoological name you can use this to detect that the name falls within the Zoological nomenclature code. See the slides below as an example and the solution to the issue.

This discussion highlighted to me that in Wikidata we should prioritise ensuring genus item quality is high to help with this effort. The adding of authorship to these names and the digital linking of scientific literature that provides the original description should be prioritised.

He then went on to discuss the name group analyzer which provided some interesting visualisations.

He then moved on to homotypic names, the consolidation of taxon names and the importance of synonyms.

Progress and challenges of a more comprehensive Catalogue of Life by Diana Hernández, Camila Plata, Markus Döring, Olaf Banki

This was a very interesting presentation on the enhanced process to improve the CoL.

The extended release of the CoL will replace the current GBIF backbone taxonomy. The presentation again discussed [ChecklistBank](#) and again reminded me to find out whether the Manaaki Whenua Landcare Research Biota New Zealand dataset <https://biotanz.landcareresearch.co.nz/> has been placed within ChecklistBank. After this presentation I checked the ChecklistBank website and it appears this dataset has yet to be added. I wonder why this might be. Unlike the New Zealand Organisms Register which is CC BY-NC-SA licensed <https://www.nzor.org.nz/terms-of-use>, the BiotaNZ dataset is CC BY 4.0 licensed <https://biotanz.landcareresearch.co.nz/terms-of-use>. I fail to see why this dataset has not been added to Checklist Bank. As one of my conference action points I will endeavour to email Manaaki Whenua Landcare Research to request they take steps to add the BiotaNZ dataset to ChecklistBank.

The presenter went into some detail about unplaced merged names within the extended release. He also discussed the issue of spelling variations and the debate concerning what to do with these in the CoL.

One question raised from the floor was whether it would be possible to do an automatic resolution with BHL species names. BHL uses the Global Names Verifier http://verifier.globalnames.org/data_sources which draws from many taxonomic name databases from around the internet. The presenter indicated that this may be difficult but the person asking the question said his group is considering working on this. There appeared to be support in the room encouraging this effort.

Taxonomic data sources from around the world to better understand biodiversity through the Catalogue of Life by Camila Andrea Plata Corredor, Diana Hernández-Robles, Markus Döring, Olaf Banki

The CoL is moving towards 1 group created from multiple sources. The presenter discussed the different types of datasets used by CoL and how they are merged into CoL addressing current gaps.

Different type of sources great outcomes

- Global multi-taxa i.e ITIS, WoRMS, PBDB
- Global taxonomic scope

Coordination	Checklists	~Names enriched
Europe	11	370,000
North America	6	330,000
Total	17	700,000

+ New names
Authorships
Synonyms
Literature

The Global multi-taxa datasets address the global scope of the project but it was pointed out there is likely a geographical bias within these datasets.

Different type of sources great outcomes

- Global management scope (build by national specialists)
 - The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species
 - Invasive Species Specialist Group ISSG

+ 21,000 names
~2,000 accepted
~19,000 synonym

+ 1,300 names
136 countries*

IUCN RED LIST

GRIIS
GLOBAL REGISTER OF
INTRODUCED AND INVASIVE SPECIES

* Data quality checks in process

The next level of dataset are the datasets with a scope of Global management. For example threatened or invasive species datasets. For example the [IUCN Red List of Threatened Species](#) dataset.

The next level of dataset can contain more challenging species and provide molecular or DNA analysis that can help to sort out taxonomically challenging species. The UNITE dataset can help CoL close the knowledge gap that exists for algae and fungi species. BOLDsystems can help address taxonomic gaps in insects as well as red algae.

The next level of dataset comes from regional sources. These datasets can help address the global south knowledge gap. This is the level of the Biotanz dataset <https://biotanz.landcareresearch.co.nz/> previously discussed.

My reasoning for wanting this dataset incorporated is that it is openly licensed and contains rich information on New Zealand species and their taxonomy. I did tweet a question about this to Manaaki Whenua during the conference

<https://x.com/SiobhanLeachman/status/1831132978799599729> but would like to follow this up with contacts within Manaaki Whenua Landcare Research in the near future.

The presenter went on to talk about checklists contributed via Plazi <https://plazi.org/>. This is helping coverage and closing gaps. In discussions with another attendee at the conference a concern was raised about errors in Plazi data. This emphasised to me that careful checking will be required before using this information in Wikidata to avoid perpetuating errors.

YOU can help to build a better COL

1. Publish or recommend a checklist
2. Issues report

Listas Regionales / gestión

GBIF ChecklistBank

Missing Chrysididae species #622

There are quite a few species missing from the *Chrysididae* family in COL, 241

The following species were existing in the GBIF species dictionary, but not found in COL:

- *Acrotoma emidi*
- *Alloconus bilineatus*
- *Alloconus gibberus*
- *Alloconus leucostriatus*
- *Alloconus neocaryus*
- *Diaprioides torridus*
- *Chrysidus nimius*
- *Chrysidus punctus*
- *Chrysidus pictus*
- *Chrysidus strombus*
- *Chrysidus unguis*

<https://github.com/CatalogueOfLife/data/issues>

The presenter then went on to ask for help to improve the CoL. As part of the presentation there was a discussion about listed endangered species in countries. These are either not published in reputable journals and so can be difficult to find. Also most are published under a closed copyright licence. To be added to ChecklistBank and therefore incorporated into the CoL they should be published in reputable journals to improve their findability and also under a Creative Commons Attribution CC BY licence.

I am aware that the New Zealand Threatened Species Classification data is CC BY 4.0 licensed. See <https://nztns.org.nz/content/COPYRIGHT>. It does not appear that this data is making its way directly into ChecklistBank and from there to the CoL. This is an issue that should be raised with the Department of Conservation and also the CoL.

Building Better Worlds - Experiences of Using ChecklistBank to Build a Composite Taxonomy for a Large Biodiversity Aggregator by Simon Sherrin, Cameron Slatyer, Tania Laity

Simon, whom I had met at the previous TDWG 2023 conference, gave a great virtual presentation giving an overview of the Atlas of Living Australia (ALA) and the work they do on taxonomic names prior to their data being ingested and reused in a multitude of projects.

In ALA, species names and occurrence data comes from diverse sources. They are not aiming to be a source of taxonomic truth. The ALA is aiming to achieve an outcome, that every occurrence record is associated with the right taxon. The ALA are working on their taxonomic backbone to improve name matching.

Note the ALA uses the New Zealand Organisms Register (NZOR) amongst others and then supplies this data to ChecklistBank.

Simon then gave a list of wishes to the CoL with the aim of making the ALA's life easier. He also gave a more technical issues wishlist.

An Introduction to the Global Registry of Scientific Collections (GRSciColl) by Melissa Jean-Yi Liu, Lily Shrestha, Marie Grosjean, Morten Høfft, Marcos Lopez Gonzalez, Tim Robertson

This presentation provided context about the Global Registry of Scientific Collections (GRSciColl) <https://scientific-collections.gbif.org/>. This is a database aiming to collate data on both institutions and their collections, providing the same with an identifier, in order to raise their visibility within the biodiversity community.

Rod Page pointed out that the identifier property in Wikidata is the code for the institution <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Property:P4090> and **NOT** the current GBIF identifier for the institution or collection. See for example Te Papa <https://scientific-collections.gbif.org/institution/2749cf1e-60d9-4b03-9c71-3763632b8f78> It is the letter code NMNZ that is currently in Wikidata for this organisation and not the identifier [2749cf1e-60d9-4b03-9c71-3763632b8f78](https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q915603). See Te Papa's Wikidata item <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q915603> and the statement [Biodiversity Repository ID](#) NMNZ. Page suggests Wikidata needs a property not just for the code but also the GRSciColl identifier.

This slide gives the current numbers summarising the information within GRSciColl. There is work being done to increase institutions as well as collections in the database and the speaker encouraged attendees to assist.

Each GRSciColl entry has a Universally Unique Identifier (UUID) and associated URLs. [Editors](#) can also add a number of external identifiers to their collections and institution entries. Currently available identifier types include:

- URL
- LSID
- HANDLER
- DOI
- UUID
- FTP
- URI
- UNKNOWN
- GBIF_PORTAL
- GBIF_NODE
- GBIF_PARTICIPANT
- GRSCICOLL_ID
- GRSCICOLL_URI
- IH_IRN
- ROR
- GRID
- CITES
- SYMBIOTA_UUID
- WIKIDATA
- NCBI_BIOCOLLECTION

Note that the Wikidata QID is one of the identifiers included in GRSciColl.

There are two types of GRSciColl record, one for institutions and the other is for collections. Without a login to the site, edits are submitted as suggestions. As a result of encouragement during this and other presentations I filled out a database form with public information on The Nelson Provincial Museum Pupuri Taonga o Te Tai Ao as it holds a natural history specimen collection. I am hopeful that this will result in the GRSciColl database being updated with this information. If time allows I would like to do similar work for other regional museums with natural history collections around New Zealand.

Capturing Taxonomic Metadata in the Structure of The Kew Gardens Herbarium Collections during Mass Digitisation by Frank Owen Max Communications, London, United Kingdom

This presentation added more detail to my knowledge about the mass digitisation efforts being undertaken at Kew. I was lucky enough to receive an in person digitisation tour by Dr Sarah Phillips <https://www.kew.org/science/our-science/people/sarah-w-phillips> when holidaying in London prior to attending Wikimania 2024. I had previously met Frank Owen at last year's SPNHC 2023 conference in San Francisco and had the opportunity to continue our discussions about the use of Wikidata identifiers during this conference.

He explained during this presentation that Kew is using the Harvard Index of Botanists to assist with disambiguating their collector name strings and linking their collectors to an identifier. This aligned with what I had been told during my in person digitisation tour at Kew.

His presentation again emphasised how important it is for Wikidatians to work on the Harvard Index of Botanists and to get these identifiers added to appropriate Wikidata items. I have been working on this dataset via Mix'n'match see <https://mix-n-match.toolforge.org/#/catalog/2099> but would like to encourage other Wikidata editors to assist more actively with this important linking work.

Day 4 Sessions

Of the sessions I attended I very much enjoyed the SYM10.1 Broadening Access, Community Science, Inclusion, Education, Outreach session. In this session there were two presentations that were particularly impactful for me.

A Model for Experiential Learning and Broader Educational Impacts in Collections: Creating an Herbarium Army for Rutgers University's students by Megan King, Lena Struwe Rutgers University, New Brunswick, New Jersey, USA

**RESULT AFTER 8+ YEARS
(and a pandemic)**

- All pteridophytes, seed plants and algae specimens got **ID updated** with current taxonomic name
- Herbarium **reorganized** into phylogenetic classifications
- **99% of specimens digitized** and available online (with only label photos for mosses, lichen, and fungi)
- **55%** with completed **locality data**
- **10% georeferenced**
- All data available in iDigBio, Mid-Atlantic Megalopolis portal, GBIF, & Bionomia.

I noted during this presentation that Bionomia was mentioned in this slide and so used the coffee break after the session to discuss this with the presenter, Megan King. This discussion resulted in me sending her an email with all the Hidden Figures CURE documentation (<https://qubeshub.org/publications/4523/1>) that I had been collaborating on as well as relevant links to the International Botanical Congress workshop resources (https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:WikiProject_IBC_2024/Resources) to help encourage her work with her interns teaching them Bionomia. She was particularly interested in the Hidden Figures CURE as it could possibly be used as a project for her interns to work on.

I also raised the issue of her institutions herbarium specimens being licensed using a closed Creative Commons Attribution Non Commercial Use licence in GBIF (see <https://www.gbif.org/dataset/1804436b-6a12-4fcc-a372-531cc23a41c4>) and attempted to convince her that the Rutgers University, Chrysler herbarium should licence their specimen images openly. I explained not only did this closed licence make me reluctant to assist transcription efforts should the herbarium create projects in citizen science transcription platforms such as DigiVol (<https://volunteer.ala.org.au/>) it would also make me reluctant to work on their collector data in Bionomia. She was receptive to these arguments however it appears this would be an institutional decision.

Harnessing local knowledge to enhance geospatial collecting data by Alison Vaughan Royal Botanic Gardens Victoria, Melbourne, Victoria, Australia

I very much enjoyed this presentation on how the Royal Botanic Gardens Victoria enriched their knowledge about the location of collected specimens by reaching out to local citizen scientists and experts in local history.

I realised during this presentation that although the Royal Botanic Gardens Victoria uses an open Creative Commons licence i.e. a CC BY 4.0 licence for its dataset in GBIF, it appears that the images contained in that dataset are licensed under a closed Creative Commons CC BY-NC licence. See for example this specimen <https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/3362052544>.

I explained to Alison that this would make volunteers such as myself reluctant to transcribe the metadata on these images in citizen science platforms such as DigiVol as well as making me reluctant to work on linking collectors of those specimens in Bionomia. After this discussion she made notes and expressed her intention to raise this issue with the herbarium director.

Unlocking the biodiversity heritage of Australia's field naturalists by Nicole Kearney

Nicole discussed two grants received by BHL Australia to undertake digitisation and outreach work. The first was a [Public Record Office Victoria \(PROV\) Local History Grant](#), which funded the digitisation of the legacy publications of these naturalist clubs and the creation of an online collection. The second, a [Wikimedia Australia Partner Grant](#), enabled the creation of Wikipedia pages and Wikidata records for the publications, people and species of particular significance to each organisation. See these links for further information on these efforts <https://bit.ly/BHLFNC> and <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13626698>.

Advancing community curation of research expeditions: A collaborative journey with Wikidata and biodiversity information standards by Sabine von Mering, Robert Cubey, Dag Endresen, Annika Hendriksen, Siobhan Leachman, Daniel Mietchen, Joaquim Santos

This was a recorded presentation on work undertaken by Sabine, myself and our colleagues from multiple institutions to create a TDWG task group on modelling expeditions <https://www.tdwg.org/community/cd/expeditions/>. The slides for this presentation can be found here

📄 SPNHC-TDWG2024__SYM17_294_vonMering-et-al. Sabine presented this remotely and then answered questions via zoom.

This presentation led me to have multiple conversations with conference attendees about research expeditions with several attendees keen to attempt to ensure that work in this area is coordinated and not duplicated. More information on these conversations is detailed in the Discussions with Attendees section below.

2 million contributions from citizen scientists accelerate the digitization of the Berlin herbarium by Anton Güntsch, Dominik Röpert, Katharina Rabe, Juraj Paule

Last but not least this presentation was fascinating to me from a citizen science perspective. Anton Güntsch presented on the Natural History Museum, Berlin's efforts in running a transcription project, similar to the Smithsonian Transcription Center.

All data is entered twice over by volunteers for accuracy. He emphasised the volunteer forum is very important as it gives assistance to new users and is moderated by a student assistant at the museum.

There is a gamification element to the work and the volunteers are extremely efficient and effective in their transcription work.

The museum is planning an expansion of the programme beyond transcription of specimen labels and is thinking about integrating the transcription platform with other data platforms.

At the end of the presentation I asked the question whether his volunteers would be interested in expanding their workflow to include Wikidata and Bionomia editing. I explained my WeDigBio workflow where I transcribe a specimen label, then I check Wikidata to see if the person has a Wikidata item. I do research on the collector either finding their death date or if they are living, their ORCID, create or enriching a Wikidata item for them, and then manually add that collector to Bionomia using either their Wikidata item if they are deceased or the ORCID if they are living. I then attribute any specimens I can to them. I explained I had “how do” documents in English if he was interested. He suggested I send him these documents and he would then consider whether this was an extension his volunteers would be interested in.

Day 5 Sessions

TDWG General meeting

I attended the TDW General meeting and obtained information on the upcoming 2025 conference which will be held in Bogota in Columbia.

Closing ceremony

It was then time for the closing ceremony where thank yous were given and I had a last chance to network with friends and colleagues before saying farewell.

Informal Discussions with Conference Attendees

Nicole Kearney, the head of BHL Australia, was attending and with me also being present and the chairperson of the BHL-Wiki working group this gave us an opportunity to discuss Wiki work in person including the current pilot attempt at reinvigorating BHL Flickr uploads.

Holly Little and I had a conversation prior to my presentation as she had read the extended abstract. She wanted to touch base about contacting me regarding a possible project the National Museum of Natural History, Washington D.C. may be running on research expeditions. I told her to definitely contact me should this come to fruition. She has previously collaborated with me on a Paleo Bionomia project and I am confident she will contact me when she needs to.

I had a discussion with Christina Byrd, Collections Manager, Vertebrate Paleontology at Harvard Museum of Comparative Zoology, about research expeditions and the possibility of that museum creating a work from home position for an intern. The intern would be able to undertake research work on research expeditions using content already digitised and placed in the Biodiversity Heritage Library.

I had several discussions with Libby Ellwood from iDigBio. Libby and I are on the WeDigBio advisory board, a meeting of this board will be happening within the next week after the conference. It was therefore very helpful to catch up in person and discuss a variety of topics related to citizen science and biodiversity data initiatives.

I had several discussions with Frank Owen, the digitisation director of Kew herbarium's efforts to digitise its entire collection. We discussed the Harvard Index of Botanists and I advocated for the use of Wikidata and its identifiers.

I had a discussion with Tokay Alberts from the California Academy of Sciences, an early career museum professional. He was keen to hear more about Wikidata and Bionomia and wanted to add collectors from his institutions to Wikidata and then to Bionomia. I emailed him information on ORCID, uploading presentations to Zenodo to generate a DOI and adding these to his ORCID, as well as resources for editing Wikidata and Bionomia.

Alyson Wilkins from the Natural History Museum of Utah and I discussed the digitisation of field notebooks and the addition of these to the Biodiversity Heritage Library. She also was interested in placing research expeditions as well as collectors into Wikidata. She was aware of Wikidata and was interested in learning more as a result of my Te Papa Research Expeditions project presentation.

Ely Wallis, Chair of the TDWG Executive and at the Atlas of Living Australia, CSIRO, and I had several discussions about the general success of the conference and, as she is travelling to Wellington directly after the conference for a GBIF node meeting, we agreed to meet up for dinner to further those discussions.

Brooke Best from the Botanical Research Institute of Texas left a comment on our Te Papa research expeditions project presentation slide deck thanking us for sharing the slidedeck and in particular the resource links as well as the link to the project final report.

Katie Grim Collections Registrar at Museum of Riverside and I had a general discussion about her work, her prior visit to NZ and to Te Papa.

I obtained an introduction to the Auckland War Memorial museum invertebrate collection manager Ricky-Lee Erickson. She is a recent hire and was aware of the Auckland Museum's engagement with the Wikiverse but was interested to learn more.

I had a very interesting discussion with Visotheary Ung about her efforts to create a Flora of Cambodia. See for example https://www.researchgate.net/publication/373039151_Do_our_Project_Delimitations_Display_a_Continued_Legacy_of_Colonialism_Towards_an_independant_Flora_of_Cambodia We also discussed collectors, expeditions and Wikidata. I offered to help if she needed it. I explained about the current bias in Wikidata and the gaps in knowledge about collectors outside the global north and encouraged her to edit Wikidata.

I had a lovely discussion with Andrea Weeks about her efforts to deliver on the [SISRIS project](#) (about which she presented) as well as her efforts to teach Bionomia and by extension Wikidata. I tweeted extensively about her presentation which can be seen here <https://x.com/SiobhanLeachman/status/1830871410585296930>

I also had several discussions with Shelley James, Collections Manager at Western Australian Herbarium, including discussions inspired by her presentation. See my X/twitter thread <https://x.com/SiobhanLeachman/status/1830841279548145757> During her project at the Cambridge University herbarium she came across numerous New Zealand specimens. Once she has transcribed these we have discussed the possibility of her sending me a list of the New Zealand collectors on those specimens for me to research and to ensure they are added to Wikidata so that she might then have an identifier for them.

I had a discussion with Gary Motz, Head of computer systems at the Yale Peabody Museum, about the possibility of his institution employing a Wikimedian in residence. I put him in touch with Jake Orlovitz who is currently assisting the Biodiversity Heritage Library with their efforts obtaining a wikimedian in residence.

I also had discussions with [Dr Elspeth Haston, Deputy Herbarium Curator](#) at the Royal Botanic Garden, Edinburgh. She is very interested in and has been working with Wikidata and is also active in adding data on research expeditions. She was also interested in, but did not know about, a recently published conference poster about the digitisation and linking of an important herbarium publication known as TL2. I gave her the link to the TL2 poster <https://e.pcloud.link/publink/show?code=qOhy6aK> and a link to the resource. <https://tl2.io/Front+matter/Introduction>

We had a discussion around this project with both of us agreeing that similar work should take place on other such publications. Elspeth mentioned that Nicky Nicolson <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3700-4884> is investigating undertaking this type of work with her doctoral students at Kew. We discussed possible examples of publications where this might take place. See for example <https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/bibliography/200637>.

I had a discussion with Dean Pentcheff from the Natural History Museum Los Angeles County. He is aware of a variety of folk that are doing independent work at institutions on research expeditions and we agreed we want to ensure this type of work is coordinated and organised in a cohesive manner. I put him in touch with Sabine and also offered to be a contact to facilitate this coordination effort.

I had a discussion with [Yi Ming Gan](#). She's a data manager from [SCAR Antarctic Biodiversity Portal](#) and a member of Antarctic node for [GBIF](#) and [OBIS](#). She is also an editor of Wikidata. As a result of my and Sabine's presentations she has joined the WikiProject Research Expeditions project and is keen to contribute to the TDWG modelling expeditions working group. I gave her Sabine's email and let Sabine know that she would be reaching out to her.

After the Conference

Anticipated follow up actions.

I attempted to keep up to date with promises of sharing documentation and resources during the conference. However there are several actions I intend to undertake once I return to New Zealand.

The first of these is to email the folk at Manaaki Whenua Landcare Research about the BiotaNZ dataset encouraging them to add the same into [ChecklistBank](#) for use by the CoL. I regard this as being a high priority as I have come across instances, when editing New Zealand species Wikipedia articles or Wikidata items, where the current species name of New Zealand endemic species are out of date in GBIF. By incorporating the BiotaNZ dataset into the CoL this discrepancy would be less likely to occur.

I also intend to email Anton Güntschi giving him links to appropriate "how to" documentation for both adding Wikidata and Bionomia to his volunteer transcription workflows.

As a result of encouragement during this and other presentations during the session on GRSciColl I filled out a database form with public information on The Nelson Provincial Museum Pupuri Taonga o Te Tai Ao as it contains natural history specimens and suggested that the GRSciColl database be updated. When time allows I would like to undertake similar work adding other regional museums with natural history collections around New Zealand to GRSciColl.

I aim to share this conference report on social media such as X (Twitter), Facebook, LinkedIn, Bluesky, with the Wikidata WikiProject Biodiversity telegram group, and the Wellington and Wikimedia Aotearoa New Zealand meetups, with WikiProject Research Expeditions participants, on the WikiProject New Zealand talk page and in the GLAMwiki newsletter .

I intend to keep in contact with many of the attendees of the conference via social media including on the platforms such as X (Twitter), Bluesky, Telegram, Slack, and Mastodon as well as through the various projects and initiatives we currently collaborate on.

I have previously met or become aware of many of the SPNHC & TDWG 2024 attendees via my dealing with their institutions biodiversity data as well as institutional/project based Wikidata workshops or participating in the projects themselves, as well as attending or presenting at other conferences both in person or virtually.

By attending this conference physically I have had the opportunity to meet or re-engage with many of these folk in this community in person. As can be seen by the conversations undertaken during the conference outlined in this report, this has helped strengthen these relationships. As a result of meeting participants in person I believe many will now be more comfortable in reaching out to me should they have queries or require assistance with Wikidata, Wikipedia and Wikimedia Commons, as well as any of the WikiProjects or work I am involved with.

Possible future Wikidata workshops

As mentioned above I had discussions with Yi Ming Gan about a possible Wikidata workshop. As well as her interest in the Wikidata WikiProject Research Expeditions she is also considering organising a Wikidata and Bionomia workshop at some point in the near future. I assured her I would be happy to assist these efforts if she wanted to reach out to me via email.

Conclusion

In conclusion I believe my Wikimedia Aotearoa New Zealand funded conference attendance was extremely successful. It assisted in raising awareness of the Te Papa research expeditions WikiProject, the overarching WikiProject research expeditions and the TDWG expeditions working group that has come about as a result of that WikiProject's work. It increased my own knowledge of the workings of important aggregators of datasets and taxon names as well as the practical considerations institutions face when linking identifiers throughout the biodiversity information ecosystem. Finally it gave me an opportunity to advocate for the use of Wikidata identifiers and the use of open licences for data and images thus hopefully improving the biodiversity data ecosystem for the better.

I would like to take this opportunity to thank Wikimedia Aotearoa New Zealand for providing funding to enable me to attend this conference.

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